

Extraction of Uranium(VI) from Aqueous Nitrate Solution with Triisoamyl Phosphate

D. C. RUPAINWAR and (Miss) S. R. JAISWAL

Applied Chemistry Section, School of Applied Sciences, Institute of Technology, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

Manuscript received 15 June 1982, revised 21 December 1982, accepted 30 March 1983

The higher homologue of *n*-tributyl phosphate viz., triisoamyl phosphate (TAP) was prepared from fusel oil and has been successfully employed for the extraction of uranium(VI) from its aqueous nitric acid solution and its separation from various cations and anions. Parameters like [TAP], $[H_3O^+]$, [U(VI)] and the effect of diluent employed have been investigated in detail. It was found that maximum extraction (95%) takes place at $[H_3O^+] = 3.0 N$ and by 20% TAP (v/v) in carbontetrachloride. The empirical formula of the extracted species has been evaluated to be $UO_2(NO_3)_3 \cdot 2TAP$. The mechanism of the extraction process has been discussed.

PHOSPHATIC solvents are known to extract hexavalent uranium from its acidic solutions much more efficiently than the other conventional solvents¹. *n*-Tributylphosphate (*n*-TBP) has been extensively used as a solvent for the extraction and separation of uranium(VI) from its acidic solutions²⁻⁴.

We have prepared triisoamylphosphate (TAP), a higher homologue of TBP, from fusel oil, a by-product of alcohol industry. TAP has been successfully employed for the extraction and separation of gallium(III), indium(III), thallium(III) and iron(III)⁵⁻⁶. The potentialities of the new solvent TAP for the extraction of uranium(VI) are reported in this communication.

Experimental

Materials: The solvent TAP was prepared as described earlier⁶. The diluent carbontetrachloride and other organic solvents were purified by conventional methods. Arsenazo(III) was used as a reagent for colorimetric determination of uranium(VI) following the standard procedures⁷. Other reagents were AnalaR grade chemicals and were used without further purification. Carbontetrachloride was used as a solvent for TAP, unless stated otherwise.

Extraction procedure: 15 ml pure TAP, appropriately diluted with carbontetrachloride, was equilibrated for 5 min with an equal volume of an aqueous solution of the desired acidity but without U(VI). 10 ml of this pre-equilibrated solvent was then shaken for 5 min in a stoppered measuring cylinder with an equal volume of an acidic solution of uranyl nitrate. Preliminary experiments had shown that 5 min are sufficient to attain the equilibrium. After equilibration, the layers were centrifuged and aliquots from both the layers were withdrawn and analysed for U(VI) content spectrophotometrically.

The amount of acid extracted in the presence and also in the absence of uranium(VI) was also determined by potentiometric titration.

Parameters such as initial acidity of the aqueous layer, concentration of the metal and concentration of TAP were varied as per needs of a particular experiment.

Results and Discussion

In the present work we have investigated the U(VI)-HNO₃-TAP(CCl₄) extraction system in which the acid concentration of the initial aqueous phase is maintained by addition of strong nitric acid.

Preliminary experiments indicated that 30% TAP extracts 95% of uranium(VI) when hydrogen ion concentration in the aqueous phase was $\approx 3.0 N$. Further increase in the acid concentration does not enhance uranium(VI) extraction (Table 1).

TABLE 1—EXTRACTION OF $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ WITH 30% TAP AT VARYING INITIAL AQUEOUS HYDROGEN ION CONCENTRATION

Sl. No.	$[UO_2(NO_3)_2]_0 = 1 \times 10^{-4} M$		D	% E*
	$[H_3O^+]_a$ N	$[H_3O^+]_o$ N		
1	0.2	—	0.47	32.00
2	0.5	0.0085	1.18	57.00
3	1.0	0.0860	4.55	82.00
4	1.5	0.054	4.88	83.00
5	2.0	0.068	9.20	90.00
6	2.5	0.096	13.28	93.00
7	3.0	0.120	19.00	95.00
8	4.0	0.142	19.00	95.00
9	5.0	0.145	19.00	95.00

* % U(VI) extracted.

To work out the details of the effect of variation of TAP concentration on the extraction of uranium(VI), three different initial acidities were selected.

The results summarised in Table 2, reveal that the conditions for the optimum extraction of uranium(VI) are 20% TAP (v/v) and $[H_3O^+]_a = 3.0 N$ which gives 95% extraction.

TABLE 2—EXTRACTION OF U(VI) AT DIFFERENT INITIAL AQUEOUS HYDROGEN ION CONCENTRATION INTO TAP OF VARYING CONCENTRATION

$[U(VI)] = 1 \times 10^{-4} M$; Vol. of aq. layer = Vol. of org. layer = 10.0 ml

Sl. No.	TAP %	$[H_3O^+]_a$					
		1.0 N		3.0 N		4.0 N	
		D	%E	D	%E	D	%E
1	2	0.69	41.00	1.32	56.99	1.85	69.99
2	5	1.00	50.00	1.85	64.99	2.707	73.03
3	10	1.63	62.00	4.88	83.00	9.47	90.45
4	15	1.77	63.99	9.00	90.00	13.55	93.44
5	20	1.85	65.00	19.00	95.00	19.00	95.00
6	25	2.33	69.90	19.00	95.00	19.00	95.00
7	30	4.55	82.00	19.00	95.00	19.00	95.00
8	35	4.55	82.00	"	"	19.00	95.00
9	40	4.55	82.00	"	"	24.00	96.00
10	50	4.55	82.00	"	"	24.00	96.00

At lesser acidities i.e. $\leq 1.0 N$, even 50% TAP gives a maximum extraction of 82%.

To determine the solvation number of the extracted species a graph of $\log D$ (D =distribution coefficient) vs $\log C_{TAP}$ (% concentration of TAP v/v) is plotted in Fig. 1. The slope of the two straight lines AB and CD, at $[H_3O^+]_a$ of 1.0 and 3.0 N works out to be 0.9 and 1.9, respectively. It

Fig. 1. Effect of variation of TAP concentration on the distribution of U(VI) from aqueous nitric acid solution. AB: $[H_3O^+] = 1.0 N$, CD: $[H_3O^+] = 3.0 N$, n =Solvation number.

can, therefore, be inferred that at lower acidity extraction is comparatively low and a unsolvated species is formed which seems to be unstable and at higher acidity a disolvated species is formed, the extraction of which appears to be more favourable.

Influence of acid concentration on the extraction of uranium(VI) :

Influence of acid concentration on the extraction is shown in Fig. 2. It is observed that percentage extraction increases gradually with increasing initial acidity. In Figs. 2 and 3, $M^A HNO_3$ represents moles of nitric acid per litre in the

Fig. 2. Effect of change of initial aqueous acid concentration on the distribution ratio of U(VI). $[U(VI)] = 1 \times 10^{-4}$, $[TAP] = 30\%$, n =Solvation number.

aqueous phase and $M^O HNO_3$ the same in the organic phase. Although the extraction increases rapidly with increase in initial acidity, it is hardly affected at acidities $\geq 3.0 N$. However, with 40% TAP there is a slight increase in the maximum extraction (Table 2). It is also observed that when the extraction of uranium increases, the extraction of acid simultaneously decreases as depicted by results in Fig. 3.

Comparing our experimental data with the work reported for the analogous solvent n -TBP for the extraction of uranium(VI) from its aqueous nitrate solution it can be inferred that nitric acid seems to be extracted first as shown from the slope of the straight line, obtained by plotting $\log [H_3O^+]_a$ vs $\log D$ (Fig. 2) and the acid is eventually substituted by the uranyl nitrate in the organic phase. Thus,

Fig. 3. Equilibrium distribution curve of nitric acid with 30% TAP.

A—Acid extracted with no U(VI) in aqueous phase.
B—Acid extracted in presence of U(VI).

on the basis of the available data the extraction mechanism can be outlined as given below :

Effect of diluents and the metal concentration on the extraction :

The effect of change in diluent for TAP on extraction of uranyl nitrate is given in Table 3 and the data shows that maximum extraction occurs with carbontetrachloride, while lesser degree of extraction takes place with solvents like benzene, xylene, petroleum ether and polar solvents like chloroform. This also confirms the formation of a neutral species during the course of extraction.

TABLE 3—EXTRACTION OF U(VI) AT $[\text{H}_3\text{O}^+] = 3.0$ BY 20% TAP USING DIFFERENT DILUENTS

Sl. No.	Diluents	Dielectric constant	D	%E
1	n-Hexane	1.84	4.55	82.00
2	Cyclohexane	2.50	3.62	78.40
3	Toluene	2.38	3.54	77.99
4	Xylene	2.30	3.23	76.40
5	Carbontetrachloride	2.24	19.00	95.00
6	Chloroform	4.80	2.78	73.60
7	Benzene	2.28	4.88	83.00

When the extraction of uranium(VI) is carried out under optimum conditions i.e. at 3.0 N acidity and 20% TAP, the distribution ratio is found proportional to the initial metal concentration.

Extraction of U(VI) in presence of other ions :

The effect of certain cations on the extraction of U(VI) was observed by mixing the solutions of their equivalent amount and the extraction was done with 20% TAP and maintaining optimum conditions for U(VI) extraction.

The results given in Table 4 show that the presence of Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Rb^+ , Cs^+ , NH_4^+ , Ca(II) , Ba(II) , Sr(II) , Mg(II) , Mn(II) , Cd(II) , Co(II) , Ni(II) , Cu(II) and Zn(II) does not affect the percentage recovery of U(VI) which can be effectively separated from these cations. However, the percent recovery of uranium(VI) is affected to some extent by the presence of Ga(III) , In(III) and Tl(III) and to somewhat greater extent in the presence of Nb(V) , Eu(III) , Ce(IV) , Th(IV) , making it rather difficult to separate U(VI) in presence of these cations.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF OTHER CATIONS ON THE EXTRACTION OF U(VI) FROM ITS NITRIC ACID SOLUTIONS ; 20% TAP, $[\text{H}_3\text{O}^+]_a = 3.0 \text{ N}$

$[\text{U(VI)}] = 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$; Vol. of aq. layer = vol. of org. layer = 10 ml

Cations added	%E Found	Cations added	%E Found	Cations added	%E Found
Li^+	95.00	Co(II)	94.98	In(III)	90.80
Na^+	95.00	Ni(II)	94.85	Tl(III)	92.00
K^+	95.00	Cu(II)	94.55	Nb(V)	90.68
Rb^+	95.00	Zn(II)	94.98	Eu(III)	87.37
Cs^+	95.00	Ca(II)	95.00	Ce(IV)	85.08
Mn(II)	95.00	Ba(II)	95.00	Th(IV)	88.86
Sr(II)	95.00	Al(III)	93.45		
Mg(II)	95.00	Ga(II)	92.64		

As far as the interference of anions on the extraction of U(VI) is concerned it is observed that although perchlorate, halide and pseudohalide do not interfere appreciably, sulphate causes significant lowering in the extraction of U(VI).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. T. R. Anantharaman, Director, I. T., B.H.U. and Prof. R. N. Pandey, Coordinator, School of Applied Sciences, B.H.U. for laboratory facilities.

References

1. A. K. DE, R. A. CHALMERS and S. M. KHOPKAR, "Solvent Extraction of Metals", Van Nostrand & Reinhold Co. Ltd., London, 1970.

2. N. F. PUSHLENKOV and N. N. SHCHEPILIL'NIKOV, *Radiokhimiya*, 1970, **12**, 23.
3. M. GENMEIN and D. GOURISSE, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 245.
4. V. YA VASIL'EV and N. N. ANDREICHUK, *Radiokhimiya*, 1972, **14**, 145.
5. T. N. SRIVASTAVA, D. C. RUPAINWAR and N. SINGH, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1973, **267**, 287.
6. B. D. PANDY and D. C. RUPAINWAR, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1979, **41**, 377.
7. Z. MARCZENKO, "Spectroscopic Determination of Elements", Wydawnictwa Naukowo-Techniczne, Warsaw, 1976.